

NuDoubt⁺⁺: A Hybrid Opaque Scintillation Detector for Double Beta Plus Decay Searches

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1. Double Beta Plus Decay

In some proton-rich isotopes:

- Single beta plus (β^+) decay is energetically forbidden
- Simultaneous decay of two protons can be allowed

Modes of $\beta\beta$ decay that decrease the nuclear charge number:

- Double beta plus decay ($\beta^+\beta^+$) $\frac{A}{2}X \rightarrow \frac{A}{2}Y + 2e^+ + 2\nu$
- Mixed mode (β^+EC) $\frac{A}{2}X + e^- \rightarrow \frac{A}{2}Y + e^+ + 2\nu$
- Double electron capture (ECEC) $\frac{A}{2}X + 2e^- \rightarrow \frac{A}{2}Y + 2\nu$

Neutrinoless double beta plus decay:

- No neutrinos emitted
- violates lepton number conservation

Scheme of the energy spectrum of double beta decay

$2\nu\beta^+EC$ and $2\nu\beta^+\beta^+$ as well as all neutrinoless modes not yet observed

2. How to measure $\beta^+\beta^+/\beta^+EC$

Challenges

1. Low natural abundance of isotopes

Transition	Q (keV)	a_{nat} (%)
$^{124}Xe \rightarrow ^{124}Te$	2863.9	0.095
$^{78}Kr \rightarrow ^{78}Se$	2847.7	0.035
$^{106}Cd \rightarrow ^{106}Pd$	2775.4	1.245

→ enrichment is often possible though

2. Suppressed decay probabilities

- Phase space is lower if positrons are emitted
- half-life $T_{1/2}$ is higher

Expected $T_{1/2} > 10^{22}$ yrs

3. Background suppression

- Other processes mimic signature
- Have orders of magnitude higher activity

→ several orders of magnitude background suppression needed

Experimental opportunity

Signature:

- $\beta^+/\beta^+\beta^+$ kinetic energy deposition + two or four coincident 511 keV annihilation γ -rays

Technology requirements

1. Strong background suppression
2. High source activity
3. Good energy resolution to resolve $0\nu\beta\beta$ peak

→ novel scintillator technologies

3a. Opaque Scintillator

Opaque scintillator confine light close to its origin:

- Mie-scattering
- $\lambda_{scatt} \sim \text{mm}$, but $\lambda_{abs} \sim \text{m}$
- Opaqueness achieved by adding wax to the scintillator: NoWaSH [2]
- light yield > 9000 photons / MeV
- Light readout via grid of wavelength shifting fibres
- Relaxed requirement on scattering length
- high isotope loading possible

Simulation: Particle identification in opaque scintillator

Morphology seen through opacity:

- e^- Short ionisation trail
- one single blob
- γ Multiple Compton scatters
- multiple blobs
- e^+ Combination of e^- and γ , short ionisation trail and two 511 keV annihilation gammas

→ Excellent PID based on event topology possible

3c. Optimised Light Collection

Opaque scintillators rely on wavelength-shifting fibres:

- Largest light loss at interface scintillator / light guide
- Improve through optimised distribution of wavelength shifter in light guide
- New fibre concept optimised in terms of capture efficiency

Traditional fibre

VS

Optimised fibre

- Wavelength shifter dispersed throughout the fibre core
- Trapping cones
- Trapping efficiency in NoWaSH $\approx 8\%$

Fibre type used in most experiments so far

- Wavelength shifter only on the fibre's surface (thin coating)
- Loss cones
- Trapping efficiency in NoWaSH $\approx 38\%$

First prototypes produced → lower attenuation length but higher capture rate

3b. Hybrid detection

Slow organic scintillator delays scintillation light

- Slow solvents
- Delay ≥ 10 ns
- Preserves high light yield
- Enables separation of Cherenkov(\check{C}) / scintillation(S)

Slow scintillator separates \check{C} and S signals

Ratio between \check{C} and S depends on particle / event type

→ discrimination power based on separation of event populations in Cherenkov-scintillation-plane

Simulated \check{C}/S ratio for signal and background [1]

4. NuDoubt⁺⁺ Detector

Combination of novel technologies:

- **Highly loaded slow opaque** scintillation detector instrumented with **optimised fibres**
- Particularly suited for positron detection → sensitive to:

$2\nu\beta^+EC$ ($0\nu\beta^+EC$)
 $2\nu\beta^+\beta^+$ ($0\nu\beta^+\beta^+$)

First prototype under development:

- 50% enriched Krypton-78 gas
- 5 bar overpressure → 5 times more Krypton dissolved
- 10 kg scintillator mass in central fiducial vessel

5. Expected Sensitivity

Background contribution:

- Radioactive contamination of fibres → mostly γ 's
- Spallation of the carbon in the scintillator → β^+ decay

Background model:

- Assuming Gran Sasso-like overburden
- Hybrid and opaque scintillator technology
- background suppression based on morphology and \check{C}/S ratio
- suppression factors up to 10^4
- Frequentist analysis in energy bins (no systematics)

Expected 5 σ observation sensitivity [1]

Sensitivity to theoretical $2\nu\beta^+EC$ half-life achieved in <1 tonne-week exposure (≈ 20 kg-yr) → Comparable reach also for $2\nu\beta^+$ decay

Expected spectrum of $2\nu\beta^+EC$ and background [1]

Loading at 5 bar overpressure using 50% enriched ^{78}Kr

Expected 90% C.L. exclusion sensitivity [1]

$0\nu\beta^+\beta^+$, $0\nu\beta^+EC$: Improvement of half-life limits by 3 orders of magnitude